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Morpho-Physiological and Growth Parameter Changes Associated with Improved Sprouting of Sugarcane Bud Chips Treated with Growth Regulator and Nutrient Solutions

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of different chemicals on improved sprouting of sugarcane bud chips. The study consisted of nine treatments (T_1 - Untreated check, T_2 - Foliar spray of 1% Urea in 15th and 25th day after planting, T_3 - Foliar spray of marco and micronutrients solution weekly twice from 10th DAP to 25th DAP, T_4 - Soaking of bud chips in 10% Seaweed extract for 2 hrs, T_5 - T_3 + Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Ethrel for 2 hrs, T_6 - T_3 + Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Ethrel and 0.1% Calcium chloride for 2 hrs, T_7 - Soaking of bud chips in 20% Seaweed extract for 2 hrs, T_8 - Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Ethrel for 2 hrs, T_9 - T_3 + Soaking of bud chips in 0.1% Calcium chloride for 2 hrs). In this study, CoC 24 variety was selected and three replications laid out in randomized block design. Significant variation in morphophysiological characters viz., survival percentage, leaf area, seedling vigour index, shoot length and root length was observed with different chemical treatments. Application of foliar spray of micro and macronutrient solution in weekly twice to each portray seedlings from 10th DAP to 25th DAP + soaking of bud chips in 0.01% etherl and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs registered significantly maximum mean values of growth parameters in plant and ratoon crop viz., tiller population, millable cane, cane length, cane girth, single cane weight and number of nodes. The same treatment significantly registered the maximum cane yield and sugar yield.

Keywords: Ethrel, macro and micronutrients, bud chip, seedling vigour, cane yield

Introduction

Sugarcane is a very important commercial cash crop next to cotton grown between 30° N and 30° S latitudes. About 75 percent of the world sugar (sucrose) is produced from sugarcane and the other 25 percent comes from sugar beet. Sugarcane is commercially planted using stalk cuttings or setts. In conventional system prevailing in India, about 6-8 tonnes of seed cane per hectare (nearly 10 percent of produce) is used as planting material. This method of cultivation is gradually becoming uneconomical, as it accounts for over 20 percent of the total cost of production besides this large mass of planting material poses a great problem in transport, handling, and storage of seed cane and undergoes rapid deterioration and decreased the viability of buds. A viable alternative to reduce the mass and improve the quality of seed cane would be the plant excised auxillary buds of cane stalk called bud chips, which are less bulky, more economical and more easily transportable seed material. Through the bud chip method, bud chip raised seedlings shall be transplanted instead of normal sett planting. This concept was evolved over a period of around 60 years. Sugarcane Physiologist was first to suggest that a small volume of tissue and a single root primordium adhering to the bud are enough to ensure germination in sugarcane. However, this technology did not scale up to commercial level due to poor survival of bud chips under field conditions. Bud chips consist of lower food reserves (1.2 -1.8g sugars) per bud compared to conventional three budded sett material (6-8 g sugar per bud). The food reserves and moisture content of bud chips deplete in a faster way compared to 2-3 budded setts which reflect in their poor sprouting and early growth. Treatment of bud chips with growth promoting chemicals might hasten up germination related metabolic process (Jain *et al.*, 2011). Thus, an experiment was conducted to know the effect of different growth promoting chemicals on faster initiation of the shoot, roots, early leaf development with higher photosynthetic

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rate and activation of essential biochemical reactions prerequisite for the establishment and survival of bud chip plantlets in the soil.

Material and methods

Field investigations were carried out during early seasons of 2015-2018 with the cane cultivar CoC 24 at Sugarcane Research Station, Cuddalore to ascertain the effect of growth promoting nutrient for chip bud raised sugarcane seedlings, and to standardize the pretreatment methods in sowing of the portray chip bud seedlings, nine treatments by adapting randomized block design with three replications. The treatments viz. T₁ - Untreated check, T₂ - Foliar spray of 1% Urea in 15th and 25th day after planting, T₃ - Foliar spray of marco and micronutrients solution weekly twice from 10th DAP to 25th DAP, T₄ - Soaking of bud chips in 10% Seaweed extract for 2 hrs, T₅ - T₃+ Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Ethrel for 2 hrs, T₆ - T₃+ Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Ethrel and 0.1% Calcium chloride for 2 hrs, T₇ - Soaking of bud chips in 20% Seaweed extract for 2 hrs, T₈ - Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Ethrel for 2 hrs, T₉ - T₃+ Soaking of bud chips in 0.1% Calcium chloride for 2 hrs.

(Note: Full strength macronutrients- KNO₃ (202 g/l) + Ca(NO₃)₂ (236 g/0.5l)+ MgSO₄.7H₂O(493 g/l) + 1M NH₄NO₃(80 g/l) + FeSO₄.7H₂O (15 g/l) and Micronutrients- H₃BO₃ (2.86 g/l) + MnCl₂ 4H₂O (1.81 g/l) + ZnSO₄.7H₂O (0.22 g/l) + CuSO₄.5H₂O (0.051 g/l) + H₃MoO₄.H₂O (0.09 g/l)).

The soil of the experimental site was sandy loam in texture with low available nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, organic carbon with a soil P^H of 6.2 and the EC of 0.22dSm⁻¹. The portray seedlings of 30 days old were transplanted to the main field and maintained as per the treatment schedule. Regarding NPK fertilization, while the entire quantity of phosphorus was applied as basal, the doses of phosphorus and potassium were applied in 3 equal splits on 30 and 60 days after planting. The chip buds of sugarcane variety CoC (SC) 24 were raised in portrays and the pre-treatment seedlings were planted on 30 days after its sowing in portrays under randomized block design with three replications.

All the crop management practices were adopted for all the treatment plots. The data on germination, the population of tillers, leaf area, leaf area index, millable canes, cane length, cane girth, single cane weight, commercial cane sugar percent, cane yield, and sugar yield were documented and presented in Tables 1,2,3 and 4. The documented data on various observations were analyzed statistically by adopting the procedures of MSTAT – C (1991).

Result and discussion

Germination (%)

The effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on germination percentage of both I and II plant crop are presented in Table 1. Significantly higher mean germination 76% was observed with the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly intervals twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) and it was closely followed by foliar spraying of 1% urea at 15th and 25th days after planting (T₂) treatment. This significant enhancement in germination with the above treatments is due to ethrel application which would fourfold increase in acid invertase (AI) and ATPase enzymes activity during bud sprouting by growth promoting chemicals. (Jain et al., 2007) also found that the acid invertase hydrolyses sucrose into hexoses and the ATPase liberated inorganic phosphorus to provide cells with carbon and energy for the synthesis of different compounds essential for sprouting and subsequent growth of the underground buds. The lowest germination percentage of 59% was recorded with (control) T₁.

Shoot and root length (cm)

Regarding the shoot length at the seedling stage, significant variation was documented among the treatments in both I and II plant crop. (Table 1) A significant enhancement was noticed with regard to shoot and root length were observed with the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs

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(T₆) with 63.41 cm and 16.23cm respectively. It was followed by the foliar spray of 1% urea at 15th and 25th days after planting (T₂), with 58.97cm of shoot length and 14.64cm root length respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the lowest shoot and root length in both the crops.

The consistent uptake of plant growth regulators along with the macro and micronutrients might have attributed for the significant physiological role of iron in chlorophyll formation and its subsequent stimulatory effect on various metabolic process of the plant to increased nutrient absorption through roots to shoots which in turn increased both the root and shoot of sugarcane.

Leaf Area

The significant influence of various treatments imposed on leaf area in both plant crops I and II are presented in Table 1. The mean leaf area values were found to be significantly higher with the foliar application of macro and micronutrients weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) with 16.06 cm². However, the data were on par with the foliar spraying of 1% urea at 15th and 25th days after planting (T₂) with 15.68cm². The lowest leaf area of 12.57 cm² was recorded in control (T₁) during the same stage.

Seedling vigor

The effect of varied treatments on seedling vigor of both the crop is presented in Table 1. The resulted in the mean performance of treatments revealed that the seedling vigor was maximum with the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice (from 10th DAP and 25th DAP) + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) with 6052.64. Exogenous application of Ethrel, calcium chloride, macro, and micronutrients might have facilitated better rooting, enhanced uptake of more nutrients and resulted with initiation and further progress of the various physiological and biochemical process, leading to higher values of growth and morphological characteristics, especially the seedling vigor. It was followed by foliar spraying of 1% urea at 15th and 25th days after planting (T₂) with 5276.88. Among the treatments, the control (T₁) registered the least seedling vigor of 3482.18.

Tiller population

The effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on mean tiller population of both plant and ratoon crops are presented in Table 2. The application of macro and micronutrient solution as foliar spraying in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean tiller population of 1,86,710/ha and 1,55,000/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. Ethrel applications might have strengthened the root activity and effectively utilized the nitrate-nitrogen for proper tiller growth. Results are in consonance with the findings of Rao *et al.*, (2005) who reported that the exogenous application of ethrel has the ability to promote the axillary bud break and increases initial shoot numbers in several species. The early and enhanced sprouting with ethrel soaked sets could have also provided an additional 25 days for physiological growth of shoots at tillering stage as reported by Rai *et al.*, (2017) moreover, Wu *et al.*, (2008) found that the enhancement in tillering of sugarcane requires energy, protein, carbon, and nutrients for development of new shoots from the mother shoot and the combined application of macro and micronutrients with the above treatment would have compensated the overall nutrients requirement of sugarcane and results in higher population of tillers.

The soaking of bud chips in 10% sea weed extract (*Ascophyllum nodosum* sps.) for 2 hrs (T₄) stands next with the mean tiller population of 1,80,750/ha and 1,53,690/ha in ratoon crop respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean tiller population of 1,52,500/ha and 1,35,080/ha in ratoon crop respectively.

Leaf Area and Leaf Area Index

The effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on leaf area of plant crop is presented in Table 2. Among the evaluated treatments the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean leaf area of 122.8cm² and leaf area index of 4.36. Leaf area index is an important in sugarcane yield deciding indices since sugarcane has a high leaf area index and high photosynthetic efficiency under ample sunlight, compare to any other crops. Variation in growth and

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productivity is closely related to the amount of intercepted radiation, largely determined by leaf area index. The higher ethylene evolution led to higher leaf area and it resulted in greater light interception and photosynthesis (Mir *et al.*, 2010).

The treatment consisting the soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Ethrel for 2 hrs (T_8) stands next with the 114.15cm² of leaf area and it was comparable with the application of T_3 (Foliar spray of ½ strength of macro and micronutrient solution will be added weekly twice to each portray from 10th DAP to 25th DAP) treatment. The control (T_1) recorded the minimum mean leaf area of 64.73cm² and leaf area index of 3.8.

Millable canes

The effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on the millable cane of plant and ratoon crop is presented in Table 2. Among the treatments, the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T_6) significantly registered the maximum mean millable cane of 1,20,930/ha and 1,19,080/ha in ratoon crop respectively. The treatment T_9 (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs) stands next with the population of 1,18,760/ha and 1,16,090/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. Ethrel induced the early emergence and establishment of tillers which eventually resulted in a higher number of mature stalks. Improvement in millable canes in the corresponding treatments might be attributed to early and higher emergence due to setts treatment with an ethrel solution and better photosynthetic efficiency resulted in the production of a higher number of tillers and its subsequent conversion to millable canes at harvest. Similar results were reported by Kumar (2016).

However, it was comparable with the application of T_2 treatment (foliar spray of 1% urea at 15th and 25th days after planting). The control (T_1) recorded the minimum mean millable cane population of 1,09,080/ha and 1,10,320/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Cane Length (cm)

The effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on cane length of plant and ratoon crop is presented in Table 3. Among the treatments evaluated, the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T_6) significantly registered the maximum mean cane length of 285cm and 274cm in plant and ratoon respectively increase in the length of the stalk which resulted from foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution as foliar spray in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs that increased the leaf area index resulting in enhanced photosynthetic activity and assimilates production in the leaves which later on translocate into internodes and thus increased internode elongation and also internode numbers as reported by Rai *et al.*, (2017).

However, it was on par with the treatment T_9 (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs) with a cane length of 282cm and 269.3cm in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The control (T_1) recorded the minimum mean cane length of 249 cm and 216 cm in ratoon crop respectively.

Cane girth (cm)

Among the treatments (Table 3) the application of macro and micronutrient solution as foliar spray in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T_6) significantly registered the maximum mean cane length of 2.66cm and 2.70cm in plant and ratoon respectively. It might be due to an increase in the length of the stalk which resulted from foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution as foliar spray in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs that increased the leaf area index resulting in enhanced photosynthetic activity and assimilates production in the leaves which later on translocate

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into internodes, thus increased internode elongation and also internode numbers as reported by Rai *et al.*, (2017).

It was on par with the treatment T₉ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs) with the cane length of 2.63cm and 2.53cm in plant and ratoon respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean cane length of 2.38cm and 2.03cm in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Number of nodes

The effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on a number of nodes of plant and ratoon crop is presented in Table 3. Among the treatments evaluated the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean number of nodes of 26.23 and 24.33 in plant and ratoon crop respectively. It might be due to increase in the length of the stalk which resulted from foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution as foliar spray in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs that ethephon significantly increased ethylene production and positively correlated with the sucrose percent in the internodes of sugarcane.

It was followed by the treatment T₉ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs) and T₅ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Etherl (Ethephon) for 2 hrs) with the mean number of nodes of 25.12 and 23.33 in plant and ratoon crop respectively and 25.04. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean number of nodes with 18.27 and 17.34 in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Length of internodes (cm)

Among the treatments (Table 3) the application of macro and micronutrient solution as foliar spray in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean length of internodes 9.97cm and 9.92cm in plant and ratoon crop respectively. Yao *et al.* (2005) pointed out that 400 mg/L ethephon raised the activities of acid and neutral invertases in internode 2 at the late growth stage, which was, therefore, promoting the sucrose accumulation in the stalks.

However, it was on par with the treatment T₉ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs) with the length of internodes of 9.76cm and 9.6cm in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean length of internodes of 5.68cm and 5.49cm in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Single cane weight (kg)

The effects of growth promoting nutrient solution on single cane weight of the plant and ratoon crop are presented in Table 4. Among the evaluated treatments the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean single cane weight of 1.92kg and 1.79kg in plant and ratoon crop respectively which is on par with the treatment T₉ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs), T₄ (soaking of bud chips in 10% seaweed extract (*Ascophyllum nodosum* sps.) for 2 hrs) and T₅ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Etherl (Ethephon) for 2 hrs) with the mean single cane weight of

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1.89kg, 1.77kg, 1.73kg and 1.51kg, 1.50kg and 1.49 in plant and ratoon crop respectively. It might be attributed to the effect of foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution as a foliar spray in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs which enhanced the individual cane weight at harvest due to more accumulation of photosynthates. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean single can weight of 1.36kg and 1.13kg in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Commercial Cane Sugar

Among the evaluated treatments (Table 4) the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean commercial cane sugar of 11.17% and 11.32% in plant and ratoon crop respectively. Being the juice quality of sugarcane is a dependent genetic factor of cane cultivars, the significant increase might be due to the positive effects of ethrel and calcium chloride as ethrel increases the activities of acid and neutral invertases thereby enhancing the sugar accumulation in the stalks. Rao *et al.*, (2005) recorded the maximum CCS percent when treated with 100 mg/L ethephon over the other treatments including control. However it was on par with the treatment T₇ (Soaking of bud chips in 20% seaweed extract for 2 hrs) and T₈ (Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Etherl for 2 hrs) with on CCS% of 10.57% and 10.53% respectively in plant crop and in ratoon crop it was on par with the treatment T₉ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs) and T₃ (foliar spray of ½ strength of macro and micronutrient solution (given in note) will be added weekly twice to each portray from 10th DAP to 25th DAP) with on CCS% of 11.29% and 11.24% respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean CCS% of 9.75% and 10.24% in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Cane Yield

The effects of growth promoting nutrient solution on cane yield of plant and ratoon crop are presented in Table 4. Among the evaluated treatments the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean cane yield of 130.43 t/ha and 127.89 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The highest cane yield was obtained in this treatment was due to the higher number of millable canes, cane length, length of internode as well as cane weight. Cane yield was increased in all the treatments over conventional planting, though the response was different in different treatments. The results are in consonance with the findings of Kumar (2016).

However it was on par with the treatment of T₉ (foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP +soaking of bud chips in 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs) with a cane yield of 128.29 t/ha and 121.49 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean cane yield of 107.58 t/ha and 99.28 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Sugar yield

The effects of growth promoting nutrient solution on sugar yield of plant and ratoon crop are presented in Table 4. Among the evaluated treatments the foliar application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly interval twice from 10th DAP and 25th DAP + soaking of bud chip in 0.01% ethrel and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs (T₆) significantly registered the maximum mean sugar yield of 14.84 t/ha and 14.58 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively. The yield was found to be progressively increased with the treatment T₆. (Foliar spray application of macro and micronutrient solution in weekly twice + soaking of bud chips in 0.01% etherl and 0.1% calcium chloride by the application of calcium chloride might have favored the faster cell division and cell elongation which ultimately resulted in higher tiller production and yield. The plant growth is also improved by the ability of the plant to uptake and receives more nutrients.

However it was on par with T₃ (foliar spray of ½ strength of macro and micronutrient solution (given in note) will be added weekly twice to each portray from 10th DAP to 25th DAP) with on sugar yield of 13.77 t/ha

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in plant crop and in ratoon crop treatment T₄ (soaking of bud chips in 10% seaweed extract (*Ascophyllum nodosum* sp.) for 2 hrs with on sugar yield of 13.01 t/ha. The control (T₁) recorded the minimum mean sugar yield of 10.95 t/ha and 11.26 t/ha in plant and ratoon crop respectively.

Low concentration of ethephon promoted the differentiation of vascular bundles and enlarged the areas of epigenetic vessels and phloem in the leaves thereby improving the inner transport system of the plants, increased the root activity and promoted the absorption ability, differentiation of chloroplasts and increasing total photosynthetic area and the chlorophyll content and the activities of the important enzymes related to photosynthesis, affected many important enzymes that were related to growth and sugar accumulation and produced more tillers, more rapid plant growth and finally higher cane and sugar yield.

Table.1 Effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on growth and physiological parameters on pooled data of both I and II plant crop

Treatments	Germination (%)	Shoot length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Leaf Area (cm ²)	Seedling vigor
T ₁	59	46.67	12.35	12.57	3482.18
T ₂	72	58.97	14.32	15.68	5276.88
T ₃	63	55.71	13.21	13.24	4341.96
T ₄	62	52.89	12.56	12.99	4057.90
T ₅	60	53.80	13.25	14.60	4023.00
T ₆	76	63.41	16.23	16.06	6052.64
T ₇	61	51.34	14.36	14.54	4007.70
T ₈	65	55.79	14.53	15.41	4570.80
T ₉	61	56.32	14.64	14.57	4328.56
CD P=(0.05)	1.81	1.53	0.48	0.54	268.78

Table.2 Effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on growth parameters of Plant crop and ratoon crop

Treatments	Tiller population (*000/ha)		Leaf Area (cm ²)	Leaf Area Index	Millable Cane (*000/ha)	
	Plant crop	Ratoon crop	Plant crop	Plant crop	Plant crop	Ratoon crop
T ₁	152.50	135.08	64.73	3.80	109.08	110.32
T ₂	165.06	147.16	80.05	4.31	117.66	113.25
T ₃	156.71	151.63	112.90	3.93	116.26	112.67
T ₄	180.75	142.76	107.05	3.91	111.87	113.07
T ₅	154.30	151.71	97.68	3.97	115.14	115.89
T ₆	186.71	155.00	122.88	4.36	120.93	119.08
T ₇	170.10	139.17	103.58	3.94	114.14	116.09
T ₈	175.06	153.69	114.15	3.96	116.61	112.92
T ₉	173.36	141.07	106.69	4.19	118.76	117.30
CD(P=0.05)	2.14	1.84	7.62	0.144	1.17	1.09

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Table.3 Effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on physiological parameters of plant crop and ratoon crop

Treatments	Cane length (cm)		Cane girth (cm)		Number of nodes		Length of internode (cm)	
	Plant crop	Ratoon crop	Plant crop	Ratoon crop	Plant crop	Ratoon crop	Plant crop	Ratoon crop
T ₁	249	216.00	2.38	2.03	18.01	18.27	5.68	5.49
T ₂	255	232.67	2.41	2.16	23.24	19.00	7.66	6.15
T ₃	265	246.00	2.61	2.50	22.31	20.66	6.56	6.19
T ₄	258	240.33	2.46	2.20	24.27	19.67	6.43	5.95
T ₅	263	256.00	2.42	2.16	25.04	18.67	7.14	6.31
T ₆	285	274.00	2.66	2.70	26.23	24.33	9.97	9.92
T ₇	262	242.69	2.47	2.20	22.54	21.00	8.44	8.14
T ₈	275	235.67	2.50	2.26	23.13	22.00	8.61	8.48
T ₉	282	269.33	2.63	2.53	25.12	23.33	9.76	9.60
CD(P=0.05)	12.84	11.50	0.12	0.18	1.38	1.25	0.77	0.75

Table.4 Effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on yield parameters of plant crop and ratoon crop

Treatments	Single cane weight (kg)		CCS %		Cane yield (t/ha)		Sugar yield (t/ha)	
	Plant crop	Ratoon crop	Plant crop	Ratoon crop	Plant crop	Ratoon crop	Plant crop	Ratoon crop
T ₁	1.36	1.13	9.75	10.24	107.58	99.28	10.95	11.26
T ₂	1.45	1.186	10.37	11.01	122.72	113.02	13.45	13.23
T ₃	1.63	1.30	10.01	11.24	123.17	115.82	13.77	13.87
T ₄	1.77	1.24	10.24	10.96	121.89	114.95	13.80	13.81
T ₅	1.73	1.22	10.50	11.04	123.88	109.08	14.22	14.62
T ₆	1.92	1.79	11.17	11.32	130.43	127.89	14.84	14.58
T ₇	1.48	1.24	10.57	11.17	125.99	115.00	14.37	14.01
T ₈	1.56	1.50	10.53	10.99	127.08	112.29	13.92	13.98
T ₉	1.89	1.51	10.50	11.29	128.21	121.49	14.45	14.38
CD(P=0.05)	0.25	0.17	0.65	0.09	3.05	2.46	0.16	0.23

Conclusion

Application of foliar spray of micro and macronutrient solution in weekly twice to each portray seedlings from 10th DAP to 25th DAP + soaking of bud chips in 0.01% etherl and 0.1% calcium chloride for 2 hrs registered significantly maximum mean values of varied physiological and growth parameters in plant and ratoon crop viz., leaf area of 122.88 cm² in plant crop, millable cane of 1,20,930/ha and 1,19,080/ha, cane length of 285cm and 274cm, cane girth of 2.66cm and 2.70cm, single cane weight of 1.92kg and 1.79 kg and number of nodes of 26.23 per plant and 24.33 per plant. The same treatment significantly registered the maximum cane yield of 130.43 t/ha and 127.89 t/ha and sugar yield of 14.84 t/ha and 14.58 t/ha.

Fig 1 Effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on germination percentage on 35DAP at shade net

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T₁- Control

T₆- T₃ + Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Etherl and 0.1% Calcium chloride for 2 hrs

Fig 2 Effect of growth promoting nutrient solution on the shoot and root length on 45th DAP

T₁- Control

T₂-Foliar spray of 1% urea at 15th and 25th days after planting

T₁- Control

T₆- T₃ + Soaking of bud chips in 0.01% Etherl and 0.1% Calcium chloride for 2 hrs

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